

POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE ASPECTS OF THE MODERN INFORMATION SUBJECT

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In modern times, information technologies are rapidly entering various spheres of society's development and serve for their development. The influence of such technologies shows its result in the lifestyle, education and work of people. Information technology has become an important factor for the development of the world economy and the solution of social problems.

The formation of the national system of informatization, its gross introduction and use in all spheres of the economy and life, modern information technologies, computer equipment and telecommunications, as full as possible satisfaction of the growing needs of citizens in relation to information, creating favorable conditions for joining the world Information community, as well as expanding the possibilities of using world information resources are

Indeed, it is not for nothing that the XXI century is called the age of technology. Young people make up the bulk of the number of creators and users of technologies, which are called the "world spider web", which is gaining popularity in Bugun. With the advent of the internet, it was possible to obtain the desired information, independent of time and space. It is no secret that the internet network contains news on social, economic-political, cultural-educational spheres, interesting information related to the life of celebrities and changes and discoveries in science.

The internet is rapidly entering our entire life. As we walk the streets of our city, at every step our eyes fall on the Centers, which we call the "internet cafe". So what are our young people doing through the internet today? True, it is important to admit that the internet has countless advantages, as well as negative aspects.

As these tools attract young people to themselves, phrases such as "generation of the Internet", "children of gugi" or "children of Facebook", "chatters", "Odnosts" appeared. This increases the likelihood that the upbringing of our boys and girls will pass into the hands of someone. Because the internet or cell phone begins to give them more "upbringing" than parents. It can be said that today's generation is not limited only to the knowledge, qualifications and skills that are provided in educational institutions.

In the information age, at a time when sources of informatization abound, this can be taken for granted. Especially for the human mind, the global struggles, information attacks, the propaganda of "popular culture" pull us even more alert. Therefore, one of the main tasks of modern education is to work with information in the younger generation for the sake of their noble goals, to form the skill of informatization to honestly distinguish lies. In order for our children to come of age tomorrow as fixed boys and girls, whose fate has connected them with the prospect of this country, and not others, we-adults – are obliged to fulfill the same task wholeheartedly.

For scammers, moralists, the Internet serves as a free space. Terrorism, pornography, the stress of various vices, the flow of any unverified information is increasing through these invisible "nets". Online games and "chat" rooms take over the minds of young people and waste their time. But it's not that the internet is standing. At a time when its capabilities are unfair, most of our users know how to turn on the internet, not knowing what other options it has. Without understanding the endless aspects of comfort and advantage, they understand that it consists only of one "chat". As if there is no other interesting world for them. We will see the "chat idlers" who are filling the internet cafes, we will easily draw conclusions that "the internet is a dating area for young people, it spoils them." But giving a one-sided assessment of the internet only in the negative aspect is a completely wrong concept.

In later times, whether at various official events or mutual Hangouts, press or television appearances, so far, everywhere the negative impact of cell phones and the internet on youth behavior is being raised as an urgent issue. It seems to us that the reason for such a reflection of modern technologies lies, first of all, in the fact that we do not sufficiently teach our children the need to use them consciously, paying less attention to the educational and educational capabilities of ICT. As a result, in some cases, modern information technology becomes not a tool for developing the intellectual potential of the younger generation, but a fun pastime.

The process of transition from a strong state to a strong civil society is developing rapidly in our country. Of course, the role of young people in this is special. As young people make up the majority of the population of our country, globalization, that is, the creation of a healthy information environment for young people in the current conditions in which there are various threats in the information space, and the provision of our children with resources impregnated with our national, universal ideas are among our urgent tasks.

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